

Supplementary Figures for “Is everything in order? — Re-thinking the boundary of the created kind” (Answers Research Journal)

Matthew Cserhati

Supplementary figure 1. Elbow plot for the Crocodylia analysis showing the total within sum of squares value for each cluster, calculated from the mtDNA sequence similarity matrix.

Supplementary figure 2. Silhouette plot for the Crocodylia analysis showing the average silhouette width for each cluster, calculated from the mtDNA sequence similarity matrix.

Supplementary figure 3. MDS plot for the Crocodylia analysis showing the four putative clusters in two-dimensional space.